

ARDUINO-BASED ILLEGAL LOAD DETECTION AND LINE TAPPING MONITORING SYSTEM USING INA3221 SENSOR

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Abstract— This paper presents an Arduino-based illegal load detection system using the INA3221 triple-channel sensor to monitor voltage, current, and power at three points of a distribution line. Current mismatches between adjacent channels exceeding a threshold trigger real-time alerts. The system also computes power efficiency, offering a low-cost solution against electricity theft and line tapping.

Keywords— Illegal load detection, Line tapping, INA3221, Arduino, Power monitoring, Current mismatch, Smart metering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electricity theft and unauthorized line tapping cause major economic losses to power utilities. Traditional manual inspection methods are slow and fail to provide real-time detection. This paper proposes an Arduino and INA3221-based system that continuously compares current across three monitoring points to detect illegal load extraction automatically.

II. METHODOLOGY

The system uses an Arduino Uno interfaced with the INA3221 over I2C to acquire voltage, current, and power from three line points in real time. A configurable threshold triggers an alert upon detecting unauthorized current extraction.

A. System Hardware and Channel Allocation

The INA3221 provides three channels: CH1 (input), CH2 (midpoint), and CH3 (load side), each measuring bus voltage, shunt voltage, current, and power. Additional parameters include load resistance, conductance, and inter-channel current difference.

B. Detection Algorithm and Power Flow Analysis

If $I(\text{CH1}) > I(\text{CH2})$ or $I(\text{CH2}) > I(\text{CH3})$ beyond a set threshold, an illegal tap alert is raised. Power efficiency is computed as $\text{Efficiency (\%)} = (P_{\text{out}} / P_{\text{in}}) \times 100$, where P_{in} and P_{out} are from CH1 and CH3 respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system was tested using a simulated distribution line with deliberate tap points. All current mismatches were detected within 500 ms, and the INA3221 provided consistent readings across all channels.

Table 1 shows the measured parameters for a tap scenario between CH1 and CH2. The 172.6 mA current difference triggered the alert, while efficiency dropped to 61.77%, confirming the detection capability.

Table 1. Measured Parameters Across Monitoring Channels

Parameter	CH1 (Input)	CH2 (Middle)	CH3 (Load)
Bus Voltage (V)	12.04	11.87	11.62
Current (mA)	485.3	312.7	310.4
Power (mW)	5840.2	3712.5	3607.3
Efficiency (%)	100 (ref.)	63.57	61.77
Current Diff. (mA)	—	172.6 (Alert!)	2.3 (Normal)

Figure 1. Experimental prototype of the proposed illegal load detection system.

Figure 1 shows the hardware prototype of the proposed system. During testing, the CH1-CH2 current difference reached 172.6 mA, exceeding the threshold and correctly triggering the alert. The measured power efficiency of 61.77% confirms significant power loss due to unauthorized load extraction.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed system successfully detects illegal load extraction using current mismatch analysis across three INA3221 channels with real-time alerts. Future work will incorporate GSM-based remote alerting and field deployment for validation.

References

- [1] Texas Instruments, "INA3221 Triple-Channel, High-Side Measurement, Shunt and Bus Voltage Monitor with I2C- and SMBUS-Compatible Interface," Datasheet, SBOS576C, 2016.
- [2] S. S. S. R. Depuru, L. Wang, and V. Devabhaktuni, "Electricity theft: Overview, issues, prevention and a smart meter based approach to control theft," Energy Policy, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 1007-1015, 2011.

